

An Evolutionary Perspective on the COVID-19 Pandemic

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Like most schools, my university in south Texas shuttered in mid-March. As of this writing we are under increasingly strict, though necessary, containment rules as the SARS-CoV-2 coronavirus (COVID-19) transforms the global face of human culture. I am blessed with a small patio, the opportunity to walk in a small park, and my online senior students in evolutionary biology. We have been tracking the evolution of COVID-19 as their graduating project, since January.

The Origins

Biologists do not classify viruses as living organisms, and you will not find them as a branch on a tree-of-life diagram in text books. Their origins are puzzling, but like living organisms they utilize DNA and/or RNA as a reproductive vehicle, so we study them. They do not metabolize, cannot move, and must take over the genome of a living cell, or host, where they issue instructions for their own multiplication and assembly.

Viruses employ two highly successful general strategies for replication. The first involves taking over the cellular machinery and forcing the cell to make multiple virus copies. Called lytic, the cell then bursts and new virus are released to invade other cells. Ultimately, viruses are transmitted to other host individuals where the process repeats in new host cells.

Think of influenza for example. In a second strategy (lysogenic), viruses insert themselves into host cell genomes and remain dormant. As living cells make copies of themselves, the viral DNAs are also copied and inherited by host daughter cells. As in the case of HIV, lysogenic viral DNAs can remain dormant for many years, but in the end, kill host cells once they activate (AIDS). During the dormancy period, viral DNAs can be transmitted to new individuals.

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All living organisms examined to date harbour viruses as part of their natural makeup. These include plants and bacteria, and other lesser known taxa. Approximately 8% of the human genome is made up of ancient viral DNA sequences acquired, and passed down, from our pre-modern civilization ancestors (ERVs, endogenous retroviruses), and close to 50% of the human genome is composed of mobile genetic elements (transposons) that can physically move in and out of genomes. Transposons play a central role in molecular medicine because they can potentially target improperly functioning parts of the genome, and insert corrected instructions. Since the advent of farming, plant-feeding insects have transmitted viruses from native plants to crop plants as well.

The Spread of COVID-19

COVID-19 is a member of the coronavirus zoonotic subgroup of viruses that causes disease in birds and mammals. Coronavirus prefer respiratory tract cells, and are composed of a lipid-protein envelope that surrounds a single strand of RNA. Viruses, and other pathogens or parasites, that kill their hosts before being passed

(infection) to other hosts are unsuccessful and become extinct. Many new diseases that cause high host mortality at the beginning of epidemics, become milder over time. A 'bad' evolutionary strategy is to kill your host before it can make and transmit, additional copies to a new host.

On March 31st, the US released estimates from 12 epidemiological models that predict a US nationwide death toll of approximately 100-200 thousand by August (millions infected), due to COVID-19. Globally, those numbers will certainly vary by nation, political system, and culture. Population and evolutionary biologists expect to see a secondary resurgence, somewhat less severe, but none-the-less significant and many months long. Until a vaccine is widely available (12-18 months from December 2019, we hope), constrained human contact will continue to be the only viable approach to slowing spread.

The Near Future

What parameters affect the near term? The first answer is containment. That is, we must change the natural selection parameters that enable COVID-19 to move from human host to human host (transmission). Viral transmission success, from the point of view of COVID-19, is highly dependent on the density of its host. That is why many governments have required citizens to remain inside of living quarters until infection levels decline precipitously. Population density is, and will continue to be, a particular problem among the poor and itinerate. Secondly, viral transmission success is also highly affected by

the number of virus particles that are actually received by a potential new host. Work with many other viruses, and preliminary experiments with COVID-19, show that the fewer the viral particles transmitted, the significantly less severe the symptoms.

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These data explain the disturbingly increasing mortality rates among health care workers in hospitals: they are regularly exposed to the most critical cases that are shedding the largest number of viruses. Any exposure whatever, is very likely to involve high concentrations of viral particles.

In the opinion of biologists, the COVID-19 pandemic has just begun, and will continue to widen. We have been predicting this very scenario for decades, and have seen dress rehearsals in the cases of the Ebola, SARS, MERS, and Zika epidemics. From a simple numerical stand point, the present circumstances were unavoidable. Our accelerated, and insistent, consumption of wild lands has simply increased our encounter rate with everything in creation that lives, 'out there'.

Lessons from our recent past teach us much about the great net of being in nature. Reports on the several Ebola outbreaks since 1976 have tended to emphasize the role of the native host reservoir, fruit bats, and partial containment by prohibition of bat trade along important African rivers. However, the initiating events had nothing to do with bat trade. Prolonged, and in some cases, severe, regional droughts (climate change?), resulted in large scale tree fruit and bat roost loss. Bats sought refuge, and roost space, in open air thatched huts of outlying agricultural communities where they shed Ebola virus in faeces and urine. Both sources aerosolize when dry, and are thus breathable by human inhabitants. Killing the human host

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quickly, proved to be a mostly poor evolutionary strategy for Ebola virus, although not ending with extinction.

In unrelated circumstances in 2004, civet cats (a relative of the mongoose) were found to be a native intermediate host of another coronavirus (SARS) in Guangzhou China, which precipitated the wholesale slaughter of thousands of animals by drowning or electrocution. Neither prevention of trade, or native host extermination, is even relevant as a solution to the current pandemic. COVID-19 has made a successful evolutionary jump to humans and is deeply, and permanently, embedded in modern humans. Its initial act of adaptation will be keenly experienced for some time.

How then, do we go about our future? It seems that questions of natural selection and adaptation now clearly rest in the willingness of each of us to transform. It is a time for those of us with the resources to so do, to learn how science is actually practiced; its benefits and its limitations.

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Concluding Challenge: Beyond Resignation

We must insist on unprecedented levels of cooperation between nations (and their corporate sponsors) to find vaccine treatments and transparently share accurate data. Successful treatments have to be equally shared by and with All. Now is not a time for resignation or cynicism, but for accepting the reality and consequences of forgetting who we are as Imago Dei, Creation-becoming. For now, and for good, we must each learn to embrace, practice, and experience solitude not as loneliness, but

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as community.
With all Creation,
we are surrounded
in, and contained
by, the Comforter,
the Advocate, the
Cosmic Christ.

